

Washback in English Language Writing Skills: The Impact of Language Assessment on Teaching and Learning

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Abstract

This study investigates *washback* phenomenon—the influence of language assessments on teaching and learning—with a focus on English as a second language (L2) writing instruction. Recognizing classroom assessment as a critical pedagogical tool, the research investigates how testing practices shape instructional strategies, curriculum design, and learner behavior, and evaluates both positive and negative effects. Drawing on recent scholarship, the study highlights the effects of washback: it can foster constructive learning outcomes or hinder progress depending on assessment design. The study addresses three central questions: (1) which classroom assessment strategies effectively enhance writing proficiency? (2) How assessments exert on overall language development? (3) What impact do they exert on learners? Quantitative data were collected from 27 students enrolled in an English language skills course at Al-Baha University through standardized test scores, structure surveys, rubric-based evaluations, and statistical analyses of writing performance. Findings reveal that assessments significantly shape writing instruction. While essential assessments for measuring progress, poorly designed tests risk impeding learning. However, performance-based assessments promote skill development and learner autonomy through self-assessment. The study concludes that language assessments yield both positive and negative outcomes, recommending future research to prioritize assessment practices that cultivate critical thinking, creativity, and authentic writing competencies.

Keywords: Washback, writing skills, classroom assessment, language assessment, performance test.

تأثير التقييم اللغوي على مهارات الكتابة باللغة الإنجليزية: أثر التقييم اللغوي على التعليم والتعلم

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الملخص

تتناول هذه الدراسة ظاهرة الأثر الارتدادي (Washback)، أي تأثير اختبارات اللغة على عمليتي التعليم والتعلم، مع التركيز على تعليم الكتابة الإنجليزية كلغة ثانية (L2). وتُعدّ التقييمات الصّفية أداة تربوية أساسية، حيث يوجّه استراتيجيات التدريس ويؤثر في تصميم المناهج وتفاعل المتعلمين. تهدف الدراسة إلى تقييم الآثار الإيجابية والسلبية للأثر الارتدادي، مستندةً إلى الأدبيات الحديثة لتوضيح انعكاساته التربوية واقتراح أساليب لتحسين التعليم القائم على التقييم. وتتناول الدراسة ثلاثة أسئلة رئيسية: (1) ما الاستراتيجيات الصّفية الأكثر فاعلية في تعزيز مهارات الكتابة؟ (2) كيف تؤثر التقييمات في تطور اللغة بشكل عام؟ (3) ما أثرها على التطور اللغوي؟

جُمعت البيانات الكمية من 27 طالباً مسجّلين في مقرر مهارات اللغة الإنجليزية بجامعة الباحة، باستخدام نتائج الاختبارات المعيارية، والاستبانات المنظمة، وتقييمات الكتابة وفق معايير محددة. أظهرت النتائج أن الأثر الارتدادي له تأثيراً عميقاً في الكتابة. فبينما تُعدّ التقييمات ضرورية لقياس التقدّم، فإن تصميمها غير الملائم قد يعيق التعلّم. في المقابل، أثبتت التقييمات القائمة على الأداء فعاليتها في تطوير مهارات الكتابة وتشجيع المتعلمين عبر التقييم الذاتي. وتخلص الدراسة إلى أن تقييم اللغة يفرضي إلى نتائج إيجابية أو سلبية، وتوصي البحوث المستقبلية على تصميم تقييمية تُنمّي التفكير النقدي والابداع والكتابة الأصلية.

الكلمات المفتاحية: الأثر الارتدادي، مهارات الكتابة، التقييمات الصّفية، اختبارات اللغة، اختبار

Introduction

Language assessment plays a pivotal role in shaping educational practices. In English language teaching (ELT), particularly writing instruction, assessments often dictate what is taught and how it is taught. This phenomenon, known as *washback*, refers to the impact that tests have on teaching and learning (Hughes 1989, Alderson & Wall 1996, and Brown 2004). Washback can be either positive or negative regarding its beneficial or detrimental impact on educational practices (Hughes, 1989). In this study, we investigate the impact of assessment on teaching with reference to the skills of writing. Language assessment appears to be a simple process of writing test (Carol A. Chapelle and Geoff Brindley, 2010). Conceptualizing factors that affect language assessment are test methods that to say examinee's language performance, examinee's language capacity of interest is behind the choice concerning what performance should be elicited, and examinee's language performance is scored (Norbert Schmitt, 2010:248).

Assessment plays a crucial role in shaping how writing skills are taught, refined, and internalized by learners. It guides instructional decisions: formative assessments (like drafts, peer reviews, and writing journals) help teachers identify students' strengths and weaknesses. This allows educators to tailor lessons to address specific gaps –whether it's grammar, coherence, or idea development (Buragohain D., 2018). Performance-based assessments give students the chance to demonstrate real writing ability, not just answer grammar questions (Suastra M. and Menggo S., 2020). Studies demonstrate that these assessments boost motivation, self-esteem, and engagement. One study found post-assessment writing scores improved significantly, with students reporting increased confidence and interest in writing (Sastra M. and Menggo S., 2020). Assessment encourages students to reflect on feedback and revise their work, which is essential for developing writing proficiency. It transforms writing from a one-short task into a process of drafting, revising, and refining ideas (Buragohain D., 2018).

The quality of the performance in a relevant way is the assumption which the examinee's score is related to the examinee's capacities that the test was intended to measure (Norbert Schmitt, 2010:248). The test score is used for some purpose, typically for making a decision about the examinee; also, it allows examinees to make decisions about their own subsequent study or to classify participants for research on second language acquisition (Norbert Schmitt, 2010:248). The complex view of language assessment grasps the fundamentals underpinning the process of language assessment. In the construct of language ability, language proficiency makes it seem simple and easily defined. Language testing researchers need to be precise about what a test is intended to measure, and so they develop the

conceptual apparatus to do so (Norbert Schmitt, 2010:249). Construct is what influences the test developers' choice of the testing method, the intended meaning of the test scores, and the appropriateness of the test use.

In reference to those mentioned above, the researcher attempted to analyze and disclose performance assessment effects on paragraph writing ability. The present study focuses on a variety of classroom assessment strategies on writing proficiency while addressing the parameters of writing rubrics, and impact by means of investigating the following research questions:

- RQ1: What are the new classroom assessment strategies to be used effectively to improving writing skills?
- RQ2: How can these assessments enable L2 learners to interact and engage in English language learning and teaching?
- RQ3: What impact can these assessments have in changing L2 learners' English language?

Literature Review

The concept of washback was popularized by Alderson and Wall (1993), who argued that tests influence teaching and learning behaviors. Studies have shown that high-stakes writing assessments often lead teachers to "teach to the test," focusing on test formats rather than communicative competence. Washback is a term commonly used by writers on language assessment to denote the influence of testing on teaching (Chapelle C.A., and Brindley G. 2010; Hughes 2013). The concept of *washback* refers to the influence that testing exerts on teaching and learning (Hughes 1989, Alderson & Wall 1996, and Brown 2004). In the context of writing skills, this effect can be both positive and negative depending on how assessments are designed and implemented. Generally, washback can be divided into positive and negative one regarding its beneficial or detrimental impact on educational practices (Hughes, 1989).

The construct is defined by an ability approach as an unobservable trait. And performance approach which aims to make inference more 'directly' from test performance to performance outside the test setting (Norbert Schmitt, 2010:250). A performance test is the actual performance of relevant tasks are required of candidates, rather than more abstract demonstration of knowledge, such as that required by tests of ability (McNamara, 1996: 6). Test used to measure writing and speaking are often referred to as 'Performance test' Norbert Schmitt, 2010:250).

When assessments are thoughtfully aligned with learning goals, washback becomes positive. Positive washback refers to the way that teachers and students are encouraged to achieve their teaching and learning objectives (Alderson & Wall, 1993). So, assessments can enhance writing instruction by encouraging process-oriented teaching, promoting authentic writing tasks, improving student motivation, and fostering critical thinking (Spratt, 2005, Cheng 1997, Weigle & Jensen, 1997).

Washback can significantly influence various aspects of teaching and learning process, namely curriculum, materials, teaching methods, feelings and attitudes, and learning (Spratt, 2005). Examination has provable impacts on the content of language lessons because teachers tend to narrow the curriculum to the areas which commonly tested (Alderson & Wall, 1993). The parts of the exam which are already taught likely carry the most marks (Lam, 1994, as cited by Spratt, 2005). Negative washback: teachers have a tendency to focus narrowly on the domain directly related to the exam (Vernon, 1956). Examination affects the time allocation in the curriculum (Smith, 1991).

When the exam comes, the past papers and the exam-related textbooks are at the greatest use (Anderson & Wall, 1993). Teachers rely on using these materials heavily because “they believe the best way to prepare students for exam is by doing past papers” (Lam, 1994, as cited by Spratt, 2005). Teaching methods and learners’ approaches to learning are driven by testing (Frederiksen, 1984; Frederiksen & Collins, 1989). Most teachers tend to alter their teaching methods to meet the demand of the test (Buck, 1988). With the influences of examination, instructors tend to teach through the exam tasks or hold the activities to develop exam skills or strategy (Alderson and Hamp Lyons, 1996; Shohamy, 1996, and Watanabe, 1996).

Tests can affect teachers’ and learners’ feelings, attitudes because they are often administered at the end of the course (Pearson, 1988). For learners, the exam can make them worry about an inaccurate reflection of all aspects of their studies (Cheng, 1997). For teachers, they feel under pressure when the exam gets closer because of the anxiety of students’ results or unfamiliar test format (Cheng, 1998, as cited by Spratt, 2005). In positive washback test, learners can get encouraged and motivated to attain learning and teaching objectives (Anderson & Wall, 1993).

Writing skills are essential in both personal and professional spheres to meet the demands of the twenty-first century. For instance, writing is the basis for developing key skills like reading, listening, and speaking (Biju, N. et al. 2024;). Additionally, consistent writing practice can boost learners’ imagination, creativity, and problem-solving abilities, as each writing exercise involves a constructive

cycle of ideation, composition, and decision making (Fajriah, 2023; Kara & Abdulrahman, 2022). However, many students still struggle to meet the writing proficiency expected by universities and employers (Stewart, Wall, and Marciniec 2016). This challenge is even more pronounced for second language (L2) learners, who often face additional difficulties in developing their writing skills due to language barriers (Safari F. and Ahmadi A. 2024). Academic writing rarely occurs in isolation; it typically references sources as a basis for writing. Students must take notes of lectures, read texts, collect information, develop thoughts, and produce an organised written response drawing from sources (Cumming 2013; Kyle 2020).

Writing is one of the three modes of linguistic expression and communication. Writing is not just a representation of speech, as it was one thought; rather, speaking, writing and signing are all manifestations of language users' knowledge, perspective and communicative competence (Matsuda, P.K. and Silva T. 2010; Canale and Swain, 1980; Bachman, 1990). The aim of writing may be 'expressive' (emphasis on the writer), 'persuasive' (emphasis on the reader), 'referential' (emphasis on reality), or 'textual' (emphasis on the text) (Matsuda, P.K. and Silva T. 2010; Kinnevey, 1971). Writing is the basis for developing key skills like reading, listening, and speaking (Abubakr Abdulrahman & Kara, 2022; Artayasa et al., 2018).

Integrated writing, also known as source-based writing, refers to a writing task composed based on information from one or more provided reading or listening sources (Safari F. and Ahmadi A. 2024). The main rationale behind using integrated tasks is to improve authenticity by simulating the kind of writing commonly found in real-world academic and professional writing contexts (Plakans and Gebril 2017; Yang 2009). The role of the teacher emerges as a major factor in many washback studies. Alderson and Hamp Lyons (1996) investigated teacher attitudes and behavior in TOFEL preparation classes and concluded that washback effects may vary significantly according to individual teacher characteristics.

Methodology: This review synthesizes findings from peer-reviewed articles, theoretical frameworks, and case studies. It employs a narrative approach to analyze how writing assessments influence classroom practices and learner outcomes.

Design

The research design used to explore the impact of language assessment on teaching and learning in English writing skills, combining both qualitative and quantitative data sources. Convergent Parallel Design, Explanatory Sequential Design, and Exploratory Sequential Design were used as mixed methods

types. In this study, classroom observations, teacher interviews, student focus groups, and open-ended survey responses were used as qualitative data sources. The quantitative data sources used, in this study, were standardized test scores, structured survey results, rubric-based writing assessments, and statistical analysis of writing performance. The subject was distributed in the first semester of students' English Language skills course of the English Language Center at Al- Baha University. Writing skills, in this course, is a significant problem for students. So, we investigate through mid-term and final exams the poor marks in writing skills section.

Participants

The study was conducted among 27 students in English Language skills course of the English Language Center at Al- Baha University. Writing skills, in this course, is a significant problem for students. So, we investigate through mid-term and final exams the poor marks in writing skills section.

Instruments

A questionnaire, interview, and test were conducted to collect data. The questionnaire and interview were used to enhance, whereas, the test was used to measure the participants' writing skills.

Data collection procedures

Data were collected by the following procedures: (1) Test was given to participants (pre-test and post-test). Students' writing abilities were measured by using writing rubric; (2) Questionnaire was distributed for both students and teachers; (3) Interview was done after the questionnaire.

Data analysis procedures

To analyze and combine both qualitative and quantitative data in a study on washback effects in English writing instruction, researcher typically follows a structured integration process that ensures both depth and breadth of understanding. Here's how it works: the writing scoring rubric result showed great difference between the pre-test and the post-test of 27 participants. Data in this research were analyzed by using excel chart data series software program, then well-constructed according to the data given by the software. Moreover, data given by the questionnaire were displayed in the form of a percentage. On the other hands, the teachers' interviews were well-described based upon the answers provided by the respondents.

Table 1. Pre-Test Results (Mean Scores by Writing Criterion)

Writing Criteria	Well-developed ideas	Logical Organization	Vocabulary Used	Variety of Sentence Structure Used	Error-free in Grammar	Error-free in Spelling	Connected Words Used	Appropriate Capitalization	Formal Language Style Used	Appropriate Punctuation	Total
Mean Score	12.6	0.7	0.9	35	0.35	0.35	0.9	0.7	0.35	0.9	52.8

Now, here is a simple bar chart to visualize the data:

This chart highlights which areas are strongest (like “Well-developed Ideas”) and which may need more attention (such as “Grammar” and “Formal Language Style”). Based on the data in Table 1 above, it can be said that participants’ mean was at the adequate to fair level. This means that all aspects of writing evaluation should be developed. Thus, teachers’ roles appear in this phase by using different kinds of pedagogical techniques to fix students’ educational weaknesses.

Table 2. Post-Test Results

Writing Criteria	Well-developed ideas	Logical Organization	Vocabulary Used	Variety of Sentence Structure Used	Error-free in Grammar	Error-free in Spelling	Connected Words Used	Appropriate Capitalization	Formal Language Style Used	Appropriate Punctuation	Total
Mean Score	22.4	1.4	5.6	35	0.35	0.35	1.4	1.4	0.35	1.4	69.7

The mean post-test score (69.7) showed a notable increase compared to the pre-test mean score (52.8). This improvement reflects enhanced student performance in areas such as well-developed ideas, logical organization, and vocabulary usage, use of cohesive devices, proper capitalization, and accurate punctuation. Table 1 and Table 2 show difference in writing criteria according to writing rubrics: well-developed ideas (12.6 to 22.4), these because of the more practices students are taken during each unit. They know how to think and generate ideas to provide good writing. Moreover, this difference highlights an increase in the students’ ability in logical organization (0.7 to 1.4), vocabulary used (0.9 to 5.6) ; and these for students’ following teachers’ instructions in doing vocabulary quizzes. The more students practice vocabulary, the more students develop their logical organization and vocabulary used. Also, there is difference in connected words used (0.9 to 1.4), appropriate capitalization (0.7 to 1.4), and appropriate punctuation (0.9 to 1.4). Students develop their writing skills after knowing how to put words

in connected sentence with appropriate punctuation such as space between words and agreement between words (e.g. verbs and nouns), and most significantly writing words in good handwritings.

During the interview, teachers reported that 20% of students demonstrated improvement in specific writing criteria, while 80% showed progress in their overall proficiency level. This disparity was attributed to several factors: students’ educational backgrounds (70%), the assessment methods employed (20%), and a predominant focus on adhering to teachers’ instructional guidance rather than addressing individual student needs (10%). When asked to propose remedial measures, teachers emphasized the necessity of designing their own examinations that align with both pedagogical objectives and the diverse needs of their students. Additionally, they advocated for increased writing practice tailored to establish writing criteria and the adoption of effective methodologies for teaching writing skills.

Results

Figure1. What types of writing assessments have you experienced?

The current study addresses English language writing assessments that teachers have experienced. Grammar-based writing tasks are the most of writing assessments used. Thus, they have impact on learners’ languages that have been showed on learners’ sentence structure used.

Figure2. How often do you feel anxious about before a writing test?

L2 learners’ attitude toward language assessment was showed in Figure 2. This figure displays that the participants are sometimes feel anxious before writing test (60%). This means that they have problems in presenting well-developed ideas and logical organization.

Figure3. Do you believe writing assessments reflect your true writing ability?

Figure 3 displayed that the participants’ believe that language assessment has impact on L2 learners’ language (60% agree). This means that writing assessments reflect true L2 learners’ writing ability. However, it shows that L2 learners’ language do change due to language assessment. Classroom assessments can play a significant role in realizing and implementing L2 learning tools and applications which can enhance student engagement and show students’ strengths and weaknesses. In English language learning, classroom assessments are effective in identifying students’ strengths and weaknesses, understanding student knowledge and skills, and measuring their performance level.

Figure 4. If yes, what changes have you made? (100% modified their writing instruction to align with test formats)

Figure 4 answer a research paper question (RQ3. How does L2 learners’ language change due to language assessment?). This means that changes have been made by teachers. The changes are taken

place in rubrics based on test criteria, time writing practice, emphasize grammar and structure, and focus on test-related genres. So, it has great impact on L2 learners’ language, particularly, in grammar and structure.

Figure5. Do you feel constrained by writing assessments when planning lessons?

This figure 5 showed that teachers’ feel constrained by writing assessments when planning lessons. That is to say, writing assessments reflect teachers’ constrained feelings when planning lessons. Thus, writing assessments reflect positively or negatively learners’ language.

Figure 6. How does writing test influence your study habits?

Figure 6 states that writing test has impact on students’ study habits. That is to say, the more practice writing is the more writing test effects. It shows that students practice writing more than avoid writing unless required.

Figure7. What motives you most when preparing for writing assessment?

This figure 7 showed that when preparing for writing assessment, getting a high score is the most motivated thing for students (40%) in comparing to avoiding failure (30%). This means that, learners have high motivation in getting high score and high motivation in avoiding failure. So, L2 learners' attitude toward language assessment is the highest.

Discussion

The dual nature of washback underscores the need for balanced assessment design. Educators must be aware of how tests influence their teaching and strive to maintain instructional integrity. Enhancing *assessment literacy* among teachers can mitigate negative washback and promote more holistic writing instruction.

Figure 1 illustrates the types of writing assessments most commonly experienced by students. The data reveal that grammar-based writing tasks, timed writing, and essays are nearly universal, with close to 100% of respondents reporting exposure to these forms. This suggests that traditional, structured assessments remain the dominant approach in writing instruction, emphasizing accuracy, speed, and critical thinking. In contrast, portfolio writing is slightly less prevalent, approximately 90%. While still widely used, its lower percentage indicates that reflective and process-oriented assessments are not as consistently integrated into curricula. Portfolios, however, provide unique opportunities for students to demonstrate growth over time. Revise their work, and highlight a broader range of writing abilities. The figure highlights a strong reliance on conventional assessments, while also pointing to the growing but less universal adoption of portfolio-based approaches. This distribution raises important pedagogical questions about balance: should writing instruction continue to prioritize timed and grammar-focused

tasks, or should it expand further into portfolio methods that encourage creativity, reflection, and long-term skill development?

Figure 2, reveals distinct patterns in how students experience anxiety before a writing test: sometimes (60%) the majority of respondents reported occasional anxiety. This indicates that test-related stress is common but situational, likely influenced by preparation levels, confidence, or perceived difficulty. Never (20%) a fifth of students reported any anxiety at all. This group may possess strong coping mechanisms or high self-efficacy in writing tasks. Always (20%) another fifth consistently experience anxiety, suggesting a vulnerable subgroup that may benefit from targeted interventions such as relaxation techniques or writing workshops. Often (0%) and Rarely (0%) no respondents selected these categories. This absence suggests that students tend to perceive their anxiety in more absolute terms (either occasional or constant) rather than moderate levels. The findings suggest that test anxiety is widespread but varies in intensity. Most students experience it occasionally, while a smaller but significant group struggles with it consistently. The lack of responses for “often” and “rarely” highlights a tendency to categorize anxiety in clear-cut terms rather than nuanced gradations. These insights can inform educators and counselors in designing support strategies that address both occasional and persistent anxiety.

Figure 3 the responses reveal diverse perspectives on whether writing assessments accurately reflect true writing ability: Agree (60%) the majority of participants believe that writing assessments generally capture their writing ability. This suggests confidence in the fairness and validity of such evaluations, though it may also imply that assessments align closely with the skills students practice. Strongly agree (20%) a smaller but significant group expressed strong confidence in assessments as accurate measures. These individuals likely view standardized writing tasks as reliable indicators of competence. Disagree (20%) an equal proportion of respondents expressed skepticism, indicating that assessments may not fully represent their abilities. Factors such as test anxiety, time constraints, or rigid formats could contribute to this perception. Strongly disagree (0%) and Neutral (0%) no respondents selected these options, suggesting that students tend to hold clear opinions rather than ambivalent or strongly negative views. The findings suggest that most students perceive writing assessments as reflective of their abilities, though a notable minority disagrees. The absence of neutral responses highlights a polarized view: students either trust assessments or question their validity. This division underscores the importance of designing writing evaluations that balance standardized criteria with opportunities for authentic expression.

Figure 4, impact of writing tests on teaching practices. The findings indicate that all teachers (100%) modified their writing instruction to align with test formats, underscoring the powerful influence of standardized assessments on classroom practices. As shown in Figure 4, these modifications are evident across lesson planning, teaching methods, and feedback strategies. Focus on test-related genres (60%) a majority of teachers reported prioritizing genres commonly featured in exams. While this alignment may enhance student preparedness, it risks narrowing the curriculum and reducing exposure to diverse writing forms.

Emphasis on grammar and structure (100%) every teacher highlighted grammar and writing tests, where measurable outcomes are privileged. However, it raises concerns about the marginalization of creativity and critical thinking. Provision of timed writing practice (60%): Many teachers incorporated timed exercises to simulate exam conditions. This practice helps students manage pressure but may also reinforce formulaic writing styles, limiting opportunities for revision and deeper reflection. Use of rubrics based on test criteria (80%): the widespread adoption of test-aligned rubrics ensures consistency and transparency in feedback. Yet, it also suggests that evaluation is framed almost entirely by external standards reverentially overlooking individual growth and authentic expression. The results highlight how assessment-driven instruction reshapes teaching priorities. While these changes may improve exam performance, they also raise critical questions about the balance between teaching for tests and fostering broader writing competencies. The dominance of grammar and structure over creativity, in particular, suggests a long-term shift in how students perceive writing –as a technical skill rather than a means of personal or intellectual exploration.

For the point, impact of learning behaviors, Figure 6 showed that (40%) of the students practice writing more frequently. This group builds fluency and confidence through consistent practice. Frequent writing helps them internalize vocabulary, improve coherence, and develop a personal style. It suggests they value process-oriented learning rather than just outcomes. (30%) of them focus mostly on grammar and structure: these students prioritize accuracy and correctness. While this strengthens technical skills, it may limit creativity if overemphasized. Their approach reflects a rule-based learning behavior. (25%) of them memorize model essays: memorization provides templates for exam success but risks shallow understanding. It shows reliance on rote learning rather than critical thinking. This strategy may help in test settings but not in authentic writing tasks. (5%) of them avoid writing unless required: This small group demonstrates how motivation or writing anxiety. Avoidance can hinder skill development and confidence. Their behavior reflects a performance-avoidance orientation.

However, in contextual writing differences, there is test preparation writing and personal or creative writing: In test preparation writing, students tend to be more rigid, structured, and exam-focused. Emphasis is on correctness, memorization, and meeting grading criteria. In personal or creative writing, students show more freedom, self-expression, and experimentation. Creativity and individuality emerge, but technical accuracy may be less prioritized. General impact, the data highlights a tension between exam-driven behaviors (grammar focus, memorization) and skill-building behaviors (frequent practice, creative writing). Students who balance both –practicing regularly while also exploring creativity –are likely to achieve stronger long-term writing competence. The small percentage avoiding writing signals a need for motivational strategies and supportive environments to reduce writing anxiety.

The analysis of student motivation in preparing for writing assessments reveals several distinct drivers. As illustrated in Figure 7, the most frequently cited motivation was the pursuit of high scores, reported by 40% of students. A further 30% indicated that their primary motivation was the avoidance of failure, while 25% emphasized the desire to improve their writing skills. Only 5% identified meeting teacher expectations as their main source of motivation.

Complementing these findings, quantitative survey data demonstrated that 78% of students engaged in weekly practice of test-style writing tasks. This pattern of behavior was further substantiated through qualitative interviews with teachers. They confirmed that such practices were largely shaped by curriculum's alignment with national examination requirements. Taken together, these results highlight a pronounced washback effect, wherein the structure and demands of high-stakes national assessments exert a systemic influence on both instructional design and learner behavior. Specifically, the emphasis on exam-oriented preparation appears to channel student motivation toward performance outcomes (high scores and avoidance of failure) rather than intrinsic goals such as skill development or teacher approval. This underscores the pervasive role of assessment systems in shaping educational practices and learner priorities.

Conclusion

The study examines how do L2 learners affect by language teaching and language testing? Washback is a powerful force in ELT, especially in writing instruction. While assessments are essential for measuring progress, they must be thoughtfully designed to support—not hinder—learning. So, performance assessment enables students to develop their writing skills. Moreover,

L2 learners' attitude toward language assessment is the highest. So, it develops L2 learners to be responsible for and capable of self-assessment in developing writing. Also, language assessment has

positive or negative impact on L2 learners' language. There is a strong reliance on conventional assessments, while also pointing to the growing but less universal adoption of portfolio-based approaches. This distribution raises important pedagogical questions about balance: should writing instruction continue to prioritize timed and grammar-focused tasks, or should it expand further into portfolio methods that encourage creativity, reflection, and long-term skill development?

The findings suggest that test anxiety is widespread but varies in intensity. Most students experience it occasionally, while a smaller but significant group struggles with it consistently. The lack of responses for "often" and "rarely" highlights a tendency to categorize anxiety in clear-cut terms rather than nuanced gradations. These insights can inform educators and counselors in designing support strategies that address both occasional and persistent anxiety.

Most students perceive writing assessments as reflective of their abilities, though a notable minority disagrees. The absence of neutral responses highlights a polarized view: students either trust assessments or question their validity. This division underscores the importance of designing writing evaluations that balance standardized criteria with opportunities for authentic expression. The results highlight how assessment-driven instruction reshapes teaching priorities. While these changes may improve exam performance, they also raise critical questions about the balance between teaching for tests and fostering broader writing competencies. The dominance of grammar and structure over creativity, in particular, suggests a long-term shift in how students perceive writing –as a technical skill rather than a means of personal or intellectual exploration.

The study identified that student motivation in preparing for writing assessments is predominantly shaped by performance concerns. The majority of students reported striving for high scores or avoiding failure, while fewer emphasized skill improvement or meeting teacher expectations. Survey data revealed that 78% of students engaged in weekly test-style writing practice, a trend reinforced by teacher interviews attributing this behavior to curriculum alignment with national examinations. Collectively, these findings point to a systemic washback effect, whereby the demands of high-stakes assessments influence both instructional practices and learner priorities, privileging exam performance over intrinsic learning goals.

Recommendations

Future investigations should prioritize the design of assessment practices that cultivate critical thinking, creativity, and authentic writing abilities. When assessments are appropriately aligned with curricular objectives, they generate positive washback, promoting effective pedagogical approaches and

motivating learners to enhance their writing proficiency. Conversely, negative washback may occur when test content diverges from instructional goals, resulting in superficial learning, diminished creativity, and heightened learner anxiety.

Moreover, the findings suggest that teacher behavior is often shaped by assessment demands, with instructional methods adapted to mirror test formats –sometimes at expense of broader writing competencies. Similarly, student behavior may be influenced by the dominance of exam preparation, leading learners to prioritize test-taking strategies over the genuine development of writing skills.

Assessment design: Future studies should explore innovative assessment formats that balance reliability with opportunities for students to demonstrate critical thinking, creativity, and authentic writing skills. **Washback effects:** Researchers should investigate both positive washback (alignment with curriculum goals that fosters effective teaching and motivates learners) and negative washback (misalignment that leads to superficial learning, reduced creativity, and heightened anxiety), with attention to how these dynamics vary across educational contexts.

Teacher behavior: Further inquiry is needed into how teachers adapt instructional practices to assessment demands, particularly examining whether such adaptations compromise the development of broader writing competencies beyond test preparation.

Student behavior: Studies should analyze how learners balance test-taking strategies with genuine skill development, and identify interventions that encourage deeper engagement with writing as a communicative and creative act.

Professional development: Future research should consider the role of teacher training and professional development in mitigating negative washback, equipping educators with strategies to integrate exam preparation while still nurturing authentic writing skills.

Policy implications: Investigations should examine how national and institutional assessment policies shape classroom practices, and propose reforms that encourage assessments to serve as tools for learning rather than solely for accountability.

Technology integration: Research should explore how digital tools and platforms can support authentic writing assessment, providing opportunities for collaborative, process-oriented, and multimodal writing tasks.

Cross-cultural perspectives: Comparative studies across different educational systems could illuminate how cultural and policy context influence washback effects, offering insights into more universally effective assessment practices.

References

- Abdulrahman, S. A., & Kara, S. (2022). *The effects of metalinguistic written corrective feedback (WCF) on language preparatory school students' TOEFL independent writing section score*. *International Journal of Social Sciences & Educational Studies*, 9(3), 182–193. <https://doi.org/10.23918/ijsses.v9i3p182>
- Alderson, J. C., & Wall, D. (1993). *Does washback exist?*. *Applied Linguistics*, 14(2), 115-129.
- Alderson, J. C., & Hamp-Lyons, L. (1996). *TOEFL preparation courses: A study of washback*. *Language Testing*, 13(3), 280–297. <https://doi.org/10.1177/026553229601300304>
- Artayasa, I. P., Susilo, H., Lestari, U., & Indriwati, S. E. (2018). *The effect of three levels of inquiry on the improvement of science concept understanding of elementary school teacher candidates*. *International Journal of Instruction*, 11(2), 235–248. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1174934>
- Bachman, L. (1990). *Fundamental Considerations in Language Testing*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Bailey, K. M. (1996). *Working for washback: A review of the washback concept in language testing*. *Language Testing*, 13(3), 257–279. <https://doi.org/10.1177/026553229601300303>
- Biju, N., Abdelrasheed, N. S. G., Bakiyeva, K., Prasad, K. D. V., & Jember, B. (2024). *Which one? AI-assisted language assessment or paper format: An exploration of the impacts on foreign language anxiety, learning attitudes, motivation, and writing performance*. *Language Testing in Asia*, 14(1), Article 45. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40468-024-00322-z>
- Brown, H.D (2004). *Language Assessment: Principles and Classroom Practice*. White Plains, NY: Pearson Education.
- Buragohain, D. (2018). *Classroom assessments for improving writing proficiency of English language learners: Innovation, interaction, and impact*. *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, 9(2), 243–249. <https://doi.org/10.17507/jltr.0902.04>
- Canale, M., & Swain, M. (1980). *Theoretical bases of communicative approaches to second language teaching and testing*. *Applied Linguistics*, 1(1), 1–47. <https://doi.org/10.1093/applin/1.1.1>
- Chapelle C.A., and Brindly G. (2010). *An Introduction to Applied Linguistics*: Hodder Education, An Hachette UK Company. P. 258.
- Cumming, A. (2013). *Assessing integrated writing tasks for academic purposes*. In E. Grabe, M. Jiang, & J. Lee (Eds.), *Language assessment for academic purposes* (pp. 23–44). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781139525147.004>

- Fajriah, Y. N. (2023). *Problem-based learning model in EFL classroom*. *Arab World English Journal (AWEJ)*, 14(1), 43–58. <https://dx.doi.org/10.24093/awej/vol14no1.3>
- Kara, S., & Abdulrahman, S. A. (2022). *The effects of product approach on language preparatory school students' writing score in an academic writing course*. *International Journal of Social Sciences & Educational Studies*, 9(3), 194–205. <https://doi.org/10.23918/ijsses.v9i3p194>
- Hughes, A. (2003). *Testing for Language Teachers*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Kinneavy, J. (1971). *A Theory Of Discourse: The Aims Of Discourse*. New York: Norton.
- McNamara, T.F. (1996). *Measuring Second Language Performance*. London: Longman.
- Matsuda, P.K., & Silva, T. (2010). *An Introduction to Applied Linguistics*: Hodder Education, An Hachette UK Company. P. 232.
- Plakans, L., & Gebril, A. (2017). *Exploring the relationship of organization and connection with scores in integrated writing assessment*. *Assessing Writing*, 31, 98–109. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asw.2016.07.002>
- Safari, F., & Ahmadi, A. (2025). *L2 learners' challenges in integrated writing tasks: Implications for writing teachers and developers of diagnostic assessments*. *Language Learning Journal*, 53(1), 53–70. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1459592>
- Schmitt, N. (2010). *An Introduction to Applied Linguistics*: Hodder Education, An Hachette UK Company.
- Spratt, M. (2005). *Washback and the classroom: The implications for teaching and learning of studies of washback from exams*. *Language Teaching Research*, 9(1), 5–29. <https://doi.org/10.1191/1362168805lr152oa>
- Suastra, M., & Menggo, S. (2020). *Empowering students' writing skill through performance assessment*. *International Journal of Language Education*, 4(2), 64–73. <https://doi.org/10.26858/ijole.v4i2.13345>
- Stewart, C., Wall, A., & Marciniak, S. (2016). *Mixed signals: Do college graduates have the soft skills that employers want?* *Competition Forum*, 14(2), 276–281.
- Yang, H. C. (2009). *Exploring the complexity of second language writers' strategy use and performance on an integrated writing test through structural equation modeling and qualitative approaches* (Doctoral dissertation). University of Texas at Austin. ProQuest Dissertations Publishing.

Weigle, S. C., & Jensen, L. (1997). *Issues in assessment for content-based instruction*. In M. A. Snow & D. M. Brinton (Eds.), *The content-based classroom: Perspectives on integrating language and content* (pp. 225–238). White Plains, NY: Longman.